

Supplementary Table 1. Availability of EvoPPI main features in other databases and web applications.

Feature	EvoPPI	APID	STRING	MENTHA	GPS-PROT	STRUCT2NET	HIPPIE	FPCLASS	IBIS
Users can choose the databases to be used	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
Users can choose to merge specific databases for the same species	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No
Compare databases from different species using BLASTP and user specified filters	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Ability to choose interaction level (depth of the network)	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
The protein sequence of the interacting proteins can be downloaded (FASTA format)	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	No	No
A permalink can be created	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Download results as a picture (network)	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes

Links to the databases and web applications in the table (last accessed on 21st March 2018):

- EvoPPI: <http://evoppi.i3s.up.pt/>
- APID: <http://apid.dep.usal.es/>
- STRING: <https://string-db.org/>
- MENTHA: <http://mentha.uniroma2.it>
- GPS-PROT: <http://gpsprot.org>
- STRUCT2NET: <http://cb.csail.mit.edu/cb/struct2net/webserver/>
- HIPPIE: <http://cbdm-01.zdv.uni-mainz.de/~mschaefer/hippie/index.php>
- FPCLASS: <http://dcv.uhnres.utoronto.ca/FPCLASS/ppis/>
- IBIS: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Structure/ibis/ibis.html>